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OPTIMIZATION OF MICROCLONAL GROWTH CONDITIONS OF THE GARNIER PLAN

Abstract: This article presents ideas on optimizing the conditions of microclonal growth of garnier plant, their role and importance.

Key words: optimization, conditions, microclonal cultivation, plants, garnier plant, vegetation period, photosynthesis process.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada garnier o'simliklarining mikroklonal o'sishi sharoitlarini optimallashtirish, ularning roli va ahamiyati bo'yicha g'oyalar keltirilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: optimallashtirish, sharoit, mikroklonal etishtirish, o'simliklar, garnier o'simligi, vegetatsiya davri, fotosintez jarayoni.

Аннотация: В данной статье представлены идеи по оптимизации условий микроклонального роста растения гарнье, их роль и значение.

Ключевые слова: оптимизация, условия, микроклональное выращивание, растения, гарнье, вегетационный период, процесс фотосинтеза.

Language: English

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The perspective of using modern information technology tools and modeling methods for solving optimization problems of microclonal propagation of plants, including data mining techniques that are successfully used in forecasting and managing process and objects in various spheres, including when solving various problems in biotechnology. The first successes of clonal micropropagation were achieved at the end of the 50s of the last century, when the French scientist Georges Morel created a regenerator of the orchid plant. This success was contributed to the technique of in vitro propagation of apical meristems of plants created at that time. Usually, scientists use the upper meristems of herbaceous plants as primary explants, and study the effect of the composition of the nutrient medium on the processes of plant regeneration and emergence. For the same purpose, carnations, chrysanthemums, sunflowers, peas, corn and other plants were studied.

The scientific researches were carried out according to the schedule of the technical task on the project of the state task “Research of the methods and modeling of the processes in biotechnology and plant systematics.”¹ Seed plants reproduce in two different ways: from seeds and vegetatively. Both of these ways have advantages and disadvantages. First of all, the disadvantages of seed propagation can be attributed to the genetic diversity of the obtained seedlings and the length of the juvenile period (the formation of reproductive

organs from the seed grass or vegetative shoot). In vegetative reproduction, the genotype of the mother plant is preserved and the juvenile period is shorter. But for many species (primarily wood-producing) the problem of vegetative reproduction has not yet been resolved. This method is based on the unique property of plant cells, totipotency, that is, external influence can stimulate the formation of the entire plant organism.

The process of microclonal reproduction is multistage and includes:

The selection and preparation of plant explants, which can be different organs, tissues, cells, and seeds of plants;

The process of sterilization of plant explants and introducing them into culture in vitro;

Production and cultivation of aseptic plants on a synthetic nutrient medium;

Microclonal reproduction of regenerative plants;

Adaptation of microclonal plants to soil conditions, while sterility of received culture plays one of the defining roles; therefore, optimization of parameters of the sterilization stage is of particular importance.

Production of pathogen-free material is the first step of controlling the viral diseases in vegetatively propagated crops. It allows a significant increase in field yield of fresh storage root. Zhang (1995) showed an average yield increase of around 40% in plots using virusfree roots. Plant tissue culture is uniquely suited for obtaining and maintaining mass propagation of specific pathogen-free plants. The provision of a steady supply of indexed

planting materials through in vitro culture appears economically and technologically feasible. However, the chemical composition of the culture medium is perhaps the most studied aspect of sweetpotato tissue culture; it plays an important role in success of micropropagation.

The obtained shootlets were rooted in MS-medium free hormones supplemented with 30 g/l sucrose. Each treatment consisted of 10 glass jars, each jar contained three cuttings. After six weeks growth analysis, expressed as the number of leaves, number of shoots, length of shoots, number of roots, length of roots as well as fresh and dry weights for shoots and roots, were recorded. The experiment was repeated two times.

Method is based on the unique property of plant cells, totipotency, that is, external influence can stimulate the formation of the entire plant organism. Concerning IAA and NAA, data could not detect any positive influence of NAA and IAA on all studied growth parameters. The lack of significant response to the IAA treatment has been previously been attributed to its chemical lability (Gamborg, 1988). IAA has been shown

to degrade in the presence of light (Dunlap and Robacker., 1998). On the other hand, David et al., (1996) mentioned that after only one week of NAA treatment, more than 90% of NAA was conjugate. The present study clearly proved that the presence of sucrose at high concentration and GA are environmental constraints leading to the enhancement of photosynthesis, or precisely, to the growth and development of micropropagated sweetpotato plantlets.

Of course, this method has many advantages over other traditional methods:

obtaining genetically identical planting material;

keeping plants free from viral and other infectious diseases due to the use of meristem tissue cultures;

propagation high coefficient (104-105 for herbaceous and flowering plants; -

104 for deciduous plants);

shortening of the selection period;

In this investigation, there were carried out laboratory experiments, modeling process, and simulation experiments for this stage.

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